

Sustainable Development in India

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Received: 12/08/2023; Accepted 31/08/2023; Published 25/10/2023

ABSTRACT

It aims to preserve social capital by investing the creating services that continue the framework of our society. It is larger view of the world in relation to communities, culture and globalisation. It means preserve future generation and to acknowledge that what we do can have impact on others and on the world. In nut shell we should not over use resources. We should always keep our future generation in mind. We should use resources in such a manner that ever our future generation can have high standard of living, space, fresh air, clean water, good education and quality life.

Key words: Sustainable Development, Social Sustainability, Economic Sustainability, Environmental Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development is development that meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

The four pillars of sustainability

(1) Human	(2) Social	(3) Economic	(4) Environmental
H	S	E	EN
U	O	C	VI
M	C	O	RO
A	I	N	NM
N	A	O	EN
	L	M	TAL
		I	
		c	

Sustainability broadly is used to indicate programs initiatives and actions aimed at preservation of a particular resource.

HUMAN SUSTAINABILITY

It aims to maintain and improve the human capital in society. Investment in health and education systems, access to services, nutrition, knowledge and skills are all programs under the umbrella of human Sustainability.

Natural resources and spaces are limited so there is a need to balance continual growth with improvement to health and achieving economic well being for everyone. Human sustainability focuses on the importance of anyone directly or indirectly involved in the making of products or provision of services.

SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

It aims to preserve social capital by investing the creating services that continue the framework of our society. It is larger view of the world in relation to communities, culture and globalisation. It means preserve future generation and to acknowledge that what we do can have impact on others and on the world.

It's about social equality, improving quality of society by giving importance to relationships amongst people. It can be encouraged and supported by the laws information and shored ideas of equality and rights.

ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

Economic Sustainability aims to maintain the capital intact. It aims to improve the standard of living. To maintain high and stable level of economic growth is one of the key objectives of sustainable developments.

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

It aims to improve human welfare through the protection of natural capital (eg land, air, water, minerals etc.) Initiatives and programs are defined environmentally sustainable when they ensure that the needs of population are met without the risk of compromising the needs of future generations.

In 2015 United nation set up 17 Goals of sustainable development which every country should follow and fulfill it by 2030.

Seventeen sustainable development Goals are-

1. No Poverty
2. Zero Hunge
3. Good health well being
4. Quality education
5. Gender equality
6. Clean water and sanitation
7. Affordable and clean energy
8. Decent work and economic growth
9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructur
10. Reduce Inequality
11. Sustainable Cities and Communities
12. Responsible consumption and production
13. Climate action
14. Life below water
15. Life on land
16. Peace, Justice and strong Institutions
17. Partnerships for the Goals

In 2021 India's rank is 120 (in the world) in SDG. Top five countries is the world are Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, Belgium respectively.

(In India) In SDG No poverty nine states score below the national average. Our aim is to eradicate poverty by 2030. In SDG zero hunger 11 states of India score below national average. Although govt. is trying hard to achieve goal of SDG by ending all forms of hunger and malnutrition by 2030. It involves promoting sustainable agriculture, supporting small scale farmers, and equal access to land, technology and markets. It SDG Good health and well being 17 states, of India are below national average. It takes into account widening economic and social in equalities rapid urbanisation, threats to the climate and environment. The continue burden of HIV and other infections deases and emerging challenges of mental health issues. Govt's effort is to improve health facility countrywide.

In SDG 4 quality education comes, In India 14 states are below national average. Gender equality aim to ending all forms of violence, trafficking and sexual exploitation of women and girl.

In SDG clean water and sanitation eight states score below national average of India main aim is safe and affordable drinking water, sanitation facilities, and hygiene for all by 2030.

In Affordable and clean energy. In India most states and UTs have been able to achieve the target of access to affordable and clean energy.

Six states are below national average in decent work and economic growth SDG. In this progress made towards promoting sustained economic growth higher level of productivity and Technological innovation. 7 states and six UTS score below the national average in SDG Industry, innovation and Infrastructure.

In SDG reduce inequalities is mainly to reducing income inequalities and promoting social, economic and political inclusion of all irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion and economic or any other states relevant within a society.

In SDG sustainable cities and communities 18 states and 5 UT's score national average in India. Its goal is to promoting inclusive and sustainable urbanisation, safe and affordable housing, building resilient societies and economic. In SDG responsible consumption and production 11 states and 3 UTS score below the national average.

Climate change is major challenge of present time. 13 states 2 UTS score below national average. Main aim is to increase natural resources such as increase in forest land, to reduce CO₂ and chlorofluro carbons.

In SDG life on land 16 states and 4 UTS score below national average of India Its main aim is protecting, restoring and promoting sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystem, management of forest, combating desertification, halting and reversing land degradation in conjunction with ecosystem and bio diversity SDG 16 peace, justice and strong institutions SDG 16 peace, justice and strong institutions India's 17 states and 3 UTs stand below poverty line. Its main aim is to promote peace rule of law an effective governance, principals of equality, human rights justice etc.

Last but not least the SDG 17 is partnerships for the goals.

In India NITI AYOJ is working under the leadership of Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi Ji. Current flagship policies and programmes of Government of India such as Swachh Bharat Mission, Beti Bachao Beti Pado, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojan, Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna, Deen Dyal Upadhyay Gram Jyoti Yojna, Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojna, etc are running efficiently in country.

CONCLUSION

In nut shell we should not over use resources. We should always keep our future generation in mind. We should use resources in such a manner that ever our future generation can have high standard of living, space, fresh air, clean water, good education and quality life.

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